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D8.5: Project Website

V.0 – November 2018

Status of deliverable: Public

Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review the present document.

Name	Company
Ilaria Schiavi, Giulia Molinari	IRIS
All Work Package leaders	IRIS, UNITO, UAVR, VERTECH, EXERGY

Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Deadline
1	Beta version: initial Review and Comment	22.08.2018
2	Submission of Final Deliverable	1.09.2018
3	Final Approval of Deliverable	16.11.2018
4		
5		

Executive summary

The present document describes D8.5: the project website of Project Ô, focusing on its goals, structure, and content. Three main goals of the website are identified in this document: to provide information and clarity about Project Ô, to make visible the communities and stakeholders where the circular water systems will be implemented, and to serve as a vehicle of communication in several directions. The first version of the website mainly achieves the first goal, but in the next updates an effort will be made to accomplish goals two and three on a more consistent basis.

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1. Introduction

Project Ô dedicates an entire Work Package (WP8) to aspects related to the communication of the project. Our notion of communication does not refer to a unidirectional flow of information from the project to the rest of stakeholders, but rather to a multidimensional sense in which different stakeholders can take part of it. It is in this spirit that our website aims to be not only a way to communicate about the project, but also a way to inspire others to do so in a participatory way.

As part of this strategy, the goals of Project Ô's website are threefold: 1) to provide timely and accurate information about the development of the project with an emphasis on the tools to be used at the demo-sites; 2) to provide a platform to visualize the demo-sites in Croatia, Israel, Italy and Spain, in which the project is being implemented; 3) to serve as a vehicle for receiving input from stakeholders, including other researchers working on circular water technologies, institutions benefited from circular water reuse systems, and decision-makers of the demo-sites where the project is executed, among others, and giving them output.

The Project Ô website was publicly launched in September 2018 after two weeks of testing prior to the launch. The name for the website was chosen by voting by the Work Package leaders. In the end, the name chosen was WWW.EU-PROJECT-O.EU. The website is hosted and maintained by the Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences partner in Germany, and it is backed up and updated regularly.

2. Project Website Structure

The key elements of the website are:

- A Home Page that visualizes the 4 demo-sites through a slider with iconic pictures, the upstream and circular vision of the project, the modules and technologies that will be implemented, the members of the consortium, and a quick contact form and social media channels. In short, the Home Page shows who we are, what we do, where we want to do it, and with whom we want to do it (as a process of co-creation).
- A navigation menu that includes the following pages:
 - About:
 - About the project: project information including its main goals.
 - About the demo-sites: information about Eilat (Israel), Almendralejo (Spain), Puglia region (Italy), and Omis (Croatia).
 - About the technologies: information about the four modules and different technologies to be employed for the re-use of water.
 - About the consortium: information about all the partners of the consortium and their main areas of expertise.
 - About the Work Packages: information about the nine Work Packages of the project.
 - Events: this page includes the main events and annual conferences organised by the consortium.
 - News: the news page is populated by the work that our members do to communicate and disseminate about the project. Up until now (15th November 2018), it includes 6 activities performed by the members of the consortium in the first months of the project.
 - The Downloads page open the following secondary navigation menu:
 - Reports: it will include the final reports that are available to the public.
 - Scientifics Publications: this page will disseminate the open access and peer-reviewed publications produced during and after the project.
 - Newsletters: this page will allow to access the newsletters generated by our team

- Communication material: this page includes the posters, presentations, brochures and flyers generated by our partners. In November 2018, the page includes 7 files in pdf format.
- Contact: This page includes different channels to get in contact with the project.
- A footer that includes our social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn), a quick contact form, the source of funding of the project and the contract agreement under a flag of the European Union, and a Twitter widget for the website.

These key elements of the website especially serve the goal 1) (provide information of Project Ô and the used tools to a varied audience), as stated above. The plan is that once we have done our field trips to the demo-sites and we have engaged with the citizens and stakeholders there, we will update the website to serve the goals 2) (platform to visualize the context of each demo-site and show stories related to the implementation of the technologies) and 3) (respond to concerns raised by stakeholders), in a more substantial way. The website is a dynamic tool that will evolve to accommodate these three objectives at the same time (please, check the milestone number MS30 in the upcoming future).

3. Content

The **Home Page** includes a slider with four pictures of the demo-sites and a brief description of them. For example (Figure 1), in this case the municipality of Eilat in Israel chose the picture for the slider. So, in some way, the demo-sites have co-created the website. The importance of this slider focused on the demo-sites is to show that the implementation of the technologies does not occur in isolation from the daily lives of citizens in particular social contexts.

Figure 1. Screenshot of Home Page. Eilat.

It also includes the mission statement of the project:

A circular and upstream vision

Project Ô is a transdisciplinary effort for the development of circular water systems based on the upstream engagement of several stakeholders.

<p>Upstream Public Engagement</p> <p>Project Ô supports the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework, and as such, is engaging with local people and communities in each demo-site to take into account their perspectives and needs.</p>	
<p>Technological and Social Innovation</p> <p>One of the core elements of Project Ô is that innovative solutions in the area of water management can only be made with the consideration of social values.</p>	

Figure 2. Screenshot of Home Page. Vision.

Our employed modules and technologies:

Figure 3. Screenshot of Home Page. Modules and Technologies.

A slider with all our partners (e.g. five of them below):

Figure 4. Screenshot of Home Pages. Consortium's members.

And the footer:

Figure 5. Footer.

The **About** navigation menu includes a secondary menu with linking pages to:

The aims of the project:

The Project Home / The Project

Project Ô aims at demonstrating:

1. A novel **distributed water network** that enables the use of alternative sources of water, such as brackish/salt water, collected rainwater, own/external wastewater owing to the following characteristics:
 - i. Ability to treat efficiently contaminants and pollutants in water otherwise unusable or very costly to use reducing pressure on (natural) resources.
 - ii. High specialisation coupled with modularity of design and closed loop control based on innovative sensors.
 - iii. Small scale specialisation and use of solar power and irradiation allowing the development of mobile plants to deal with low volumes of water difficult to reach.
2. A **Multi-user Collaborative Platform** allowing water systems authorities and regulators as well as water users to evaluate the overall effects of introducing and regulating small water management loops.
3. **Integrated and participative approaches to water planning** involving directly the community and the territory fostering social innovation.

Figure 6. Screenshot of 'About the Project'.

The demo-sites:

Home [About](#) Events News Downloads Contact

Demo-sites Home / Demo-sites

Lasting four years, the project demonstrates the efficacy and efficiency of planning and technology tools for a circular economy, and an integrated and symbiotic use of water in four different sites, of which two are water utility-driven (Puglia region, Italy, and Almendralejo, Spain), and two business-driven (an inland, salt water aquaculture facility in Eilat, Israel, and Omis, Croatia). While demonstrating technologies and platforms, the project interfaces water resource and spatial planning and fosters social innovation for achieving co-creation and public ownership of the innovative approaches and technologies proposed.

Figure 7. Screenshot of 'About the demo-sites'.

The Consortium:

Project Ô consortium includes twenty-one partners, which can be grouped as follows:

- **Water treatment technology providers:** IRIS srl, University of Turin (UNITO), Aalborg University (AAU), Nanoquimia (NanoQ), Technion, CNRS, National Center of Mariculture (IOLR)
- **Sustainability and circular economy specialists:** Vertech Group (VER Group) and Exergy (EXERGY), Kalundborg Symbiotic Center (KLB)
- **Systemic issues specialists – water regulation and planning aspects:** Polytechnic of Milan – Hydro Informatic Group (PolIMI), and Aveiro University (UAVE)
- **Communication and stakeholders management specialists:** Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences (HSRW) and Heim.Art –Kulturverein-Flussig (HEIM.ART)
- **Demonstration sites (location, interest group):** Demo-site 1 Puglia (Regione Puglia, planning; Acquedotto Pugliese, water utility); Demo-site 2 Almendralejo (SOCAMEX, water utility and wastewater plants specialist); Demo-site 3 Eilat (IOLR, aquaculture specialist; Eilat Municipality, water utility and planning)
- **(Local) exploitation enablers:** Particula Group and others
- **Standardisation body:** Ente Italiano di Normazione (UNI)

Figure 8. Screenshot of 'About the consortium'.

The Work Packages:

Work packages

- Project Ô is part of the ICT4 Water Cluster, and is divided into 9 work packages with the following objectives:

WP 1 – Management:

- Ensuring the effective management of the project within time and budget constraints at the highest level of quality with active communication with the EU.
- Coordinating project partners and Advisory group to achieve synergy in collaboration.
- Defining data management strategy.

WP 2 – Small water management loop technologies enabling water treatment and reuse:

- This WP has as main objectives the development and validation of the technologies to be installed at the demo sites.

WP 3 – Integrated water management, planning and circular economy:

- To provide evidence-based knowledge regarding the framework conditions that may hinder or facilitate the transition.
- To a water-circular economy.
- To assess the bottlenecks of integrating water circular economy approaches into current water resources planning and spatial planning institutional frameworks to identify innovative approaches.
- To foster its integration through innovative regulations, planning and governance schemes.

Figure 9. Screenshot of 'About the Work Packages'.

The **Events** page consists of the events organised by the Consortium:

Project Ô Kick-off Meeting in Torino

From 20th to 21st of June 2018, the kick-off meeting of Project Ô took place in Torino (Italy). More than 40 experts from different countries and academic disciplines gathered to discuss about the project work-plan for next steps.

Figure 10. Events organised by the Consortium.

The **News** page of the website is dedicated to the workshops, symposiums or public meetings in which members of the consortium participate:

Project Ô Home About Events News Downloads Contact

News Home / News

Project Ô at the Smart City Expo World Congress

Yolanda Ballesteros (Socamex) introduced Project Ô to a variety of panelists at the Smart City Expo World Congress that took place in Barcelona, Spain, in November 2018. Yolanda demonstrated that Project Ô has solutions to some of the challenges of the circular economy.

Project Ô at the 3rd Iberoamerican Adsorción Symposium

The 3rd Iberoamerican Adsorción Symposium (IBA-3) will take place on 5-7 September 2018 at the Palacio de Congresos in Gijón, Asturias, Spain. A representative of Project Ô will be present in the Poster area and available to answer any questions.

Workshops on Circular Water in Latin America

In September, the representatives of WP8, Alexander Gerber and Francesc Rodríguez, co-organized and participated in several workshops and meetings in Argentina, Costa Rica and México. One of the main focuses of the workshops was the issue of water and water management.

Summer School on "Micropollutant Analysis and Abatement"

Alessandro Cedrino (IRIS, s.r.l.) presented the talk called "Project Ô: Modular treatment technologies enabling the integrated and symbiotic use of water on a small scale" as part of the International Summer School on "Micropollutant Analysis and Abatement" celebrated in August 2018 in Denmark.

Figure 11. Screenshot of news.

Downloads includes downloadable material in pdf format (e.g. Communication Material includes posters, presentations, and flyers):

Figure 12. Screenshot of Communication Material, posters & presentations.

The **Contact** page includes the details of the project leader:

Project Ô

Home About Events News Downloads Contact

Contact

Home / Contact

Project Lead: Ilaria Schiavi,
Orbassano office and lab, Via Papa
Giovanni Paolo Secondo, 26
Orbassano (TO) 10043 - Italy,
Europe.
Phone +39 011 347 3069
Email info@eu-project-o.eu

Quick contact

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Figure13. Screenshot of Contact page.

4. Conclusions and next steps

This document has presented the first version of the Project Ô website. This first version of the website mainly has an informative function, but as the project progresses, the website will be populated with stories that are close to the demands and perspectives of the people living near the demo-sites and the stakeholders involved with the implementation of circular water technologies. For example, the website will include opportunities for public and stakeholder participation in the different events that will take place in the demo-sites. In addition, additional pages, informative videos, navigation items and sections will be added during the development of the project. The goal will always be to improve the website and provide the best experience to visitors, especially those in relation to the implementation sites and the circular water management industry.